

Detection of genetic variability in dairy cattle infectivity for bovine tuberculosis

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SUPPLEMENTAL MATERIAL

Figure S1. MCMCglmm posterior predictive check for zero-inflation. The grey bars show the posterior distribution of zero secondary cases predicted by fitting the Generalized Linear Mixed Poisson Model to the data. The observed number of zero secondary cases, shown by the red line, coincides with the mode of the posterior distribution, indicating no additional zero-inflation over the one already captured by the Poisson model.

Figure S2. The posterior distribution of sire variance for Poisson (a), zero-inflated Poisson (ZIP; b), hurdle (c), and geometric (d) models

Figure S3. Model concordance with regards to the 10% sires with the highest (a) and 10% lowest (b) infectivity EBV.